

EOSINOPHILIC FASCIITIS

Singh YP, Grover S, Gupta RK*, Krishnani N#, Agarwal V

ABSTRACT: Eosinophilic fasciitis is a rare condition that presents with skin thickening involving the extremities, and sparing the hands. Raynaud's phenomenon is usually absent. It is characterized by eosinophilia and infiltration of skin and subcutaneous tissue by mixed inflammatory infiltrate including eosinophils. We present a middle-aged man who presented with generalized myalgia involving the pelvic and shoulder girdle, and skin tightening over the trunk, arms, forearms and thighs and legs, with sparing of the fingers and toes of 2 months duration. Investigations showed peripheral eosinophilia, inflammation in the deep dermis and subcutis and fascia on histopathological examination and fascial thickening on magnetic resonance imaging.

Key words : Raynaud's phenomenon, Myositis, Fascial thickening.

A 55-year-old farmer presented with acute onset, progressive, generalized myalgia predominantly involving the pelvic and shoulder girdle, and skin tightening of 2 months duration. Skin tightening was marked over the trunk, arms, forearms, thighs and legs, however hands and feet were spared. There was no history of Raynaud's phenomenon, gastroesophageal reflux symptoms, dry cough, breathlessness, digital tip ulcers, and abdominal pain or recurrent diarrhea. He lost 4 kg body weight over 2 months. He did not suffer from comorbid conditions like diabetes or hypertension. Examination showed normal vitals with tender induration of the skin over the arms, forearms, legs, and abdomen (Fig 1). The hands, feet, face and neck were spared. Mouth opening was adequate (4.5 cm). Rest of the general and systemic examination was unremarkable. Laboratory evaluation revealed hemoglobin 13.1 g/dl, total leukocyte count 15,400 cells/mm³, polymorphs 71%, lymphocytes 18% and eosinophils 11%, platelet count 3.81 lacs/mm³ and erythrocyte sedimentation rate of 28 mm. Renal and liver function tests, muscle enzymes, serology for antinuclear antibody, urine and serum electrophoresis, skeletal survey and radiograph of the chest and ultrasonogram of the abdomen were normal. Bone marrow examination was normal. Skin biopsy from the right forearm showed evidence of inflammation in the deep dermis and fascial planes. Magnetic resonance imaging of the both the forearms showed thickening and low to intermediate signal intensity of the superficial and deep fascia on T1-weighted images. Gradient echo T2-weighted images demonstrated high signal intensity of the thickened

Fig 1: Photograph of forearm showing 'Groove sign'

fascia (Fig 2). With a diagnosis of eosinophilic fasciitis he was started on prednisolone 1 mg/kg/day and had partial response in skin tightening over next 3 months.

Discussion

Eosinophilic fasciitis is a rare disease of unknown etiology and pathogenesis. It is a scleroderma-like illness characterized by inflammation and thickening of deep fascia, first described in 1974¹. It is differentiated from scleroderma by absence of Raynaud's phenomenon and visceral organ involvement. EF occurs at all ages, with the age of onset ranging from 2 to 73 years. Onset is acute or subacute, starting as symmetrical swelling and pain of extremities followed by induration and joint contractures. Sites most commonly involved are forearms, legs, hands, and feet and involved skin appears shiny and erythematous, which later becomes taut and woody. The skin is restricted by the subcutaneous tissue and patients often have a "groove sign" (Fig 1). It may be associated with fever, myalgia, peripheral entrapment neuropathies, arthritis, tenosynovitis and rarely may present

Department of Clinical Immunology, Radiology*, and Pathology#
Sanjay Gandhi Postgraduate Institute of Medical Sciences,
Raebareli Road, Lucknow.

Address for Correspondence:

Dr Vikas Agarwal,
Assistant Professor,
Department of Immunology,
Raebareli road, SGPGIMS,
Lucknow, 226014
Email: vikasagr@sgpgi.ac.in

Fig 2: Magnetic resonance imaging bilateral forearms (axial view), fat suppressed image, showing thickening of the superficial and deep fascia.

with pleural, pericardial and pulmonary parenchymal involvement^{2,3}. Laboratory abnormalities include peripheral eosinophilia, polyclonal hypergammaglobulinemia and absence of autoantibodies. Various hematological alterations like anemia, thrombocytopenia, pancytopenia, hemolytic anemia, lymphadenopathy, pernicious anemia and association with hematological malignancies, like Hodgkin's disease, non-Hodgkin's lymphoma, angioimmunoblastic lymphadenopathy and monoclonal gammopathy have been reported^{4,5}. Case reports of association with autoimmune thyroid disease, common variable immunodeficiency and drugs like simvastatin, heparin, and fosinopril have also been reported⁶⁻¹⁰. However none was observed in our patient.

The pathogenesis of EF is not exactly clear. However, dermal fibroblasts under the influence of eosinophilic proteins like major basis protein and platelet cytokines like TGF- β produce excessive collagen and extracellular matrix proteins. These fibroblasts display increased type I collagen RNA levels^{11,12}. Recently contribution of Th1 and Th2 cytokines have been studied in EF and it has shown high production of IL-5 and IL-10 and elevated levels of Th1 cytokines¹³.

The diagnosis of EF is established by histopathological findings of a "full-thickness biopsy" from epidermis to muscle. The characteristic appearance is that of a thickened and edematous deep fascia with the presence of a variable mixture of lymphocytes, plasma cells and eosinophils. Until recently, noninvasive modalities like imaging played little if any role in the diagnosis of this condition. Radiographs may reveal soft tissue swelling and possible osteopenia, but they cannot reveal inflammation of the fascia. However, MRI is sensitive tool to allow accurate differentiation among various soft tissue structures with similar signal intensities. The fascia, a thin fibrous structure, is normally of lower signal intensity than muscle and fat on all MRI sequences. A recent study from Mayo clinic has looked at the spectrum of MRI findings in 6 patients with EF. Fascial thickening, hyperintense signal within in the fascia on the fluid sensitive sequences, and fascial enhancement after contrast administration has been described

as characteristic findings of EF¹⁴. In our patient, MRI of both the forearms showed mild superficial and deep fascial thickening with increased signal intensity relative to muscle on T1 weighed images. T2 weighted image showed moderately increased signal intensity within the superficial and deep fascial layers. Axial fat suppressed T1 weighted images showed intense superficial and deep fascial enhancement post contrast administration. MRI characteristics may also reflect clinical disease activity with the degree of T2 signal hyperintensity within the fascia, fascial thickening on T1 weighted images, and fascial enhancement all paralleling disease activity. In the Mayo clinic series, of the three patients with serial evaluations that included imaging after treatment with corticosteroids, the posttherapy images showed marked improvement in two and mild but definite improvement in the other. Though the numbers were small, the Mayo clinic series suggests that MRI can play an important role not only in the diagnosis but also in the management of EF.

Once the diagnosis is established, glucocorticoids help in suppression of the peripheral and tissue eosinophilia and limb discomfort. Patients presenting early in the illness (<1 year) show marked improvement on glucocorticoids as compared to those who present late⁴. Role of hydroxychloroquine, methotrexate, and D-penicillamine, remains controversial. Anecdotal reports of successful treatment with cyclosporine, photochemotherapy and H-2 blockers have never been confirmed in large patient population.

The prognosis of EF is still not clear. Acute onset, elevated ESR, hypergammaglobulinemia and eosinophilia has been reported to predict good response however, spontaneous improvements and frequent relapses long after the cessation of the therapy makes the natural history of EF unreliable and evaluation of any therapy difficult. A recent series from Spain, which had ten patients over a period of ten years found that the clinical course of EF was inadequate and the treatment response poor in patients with spreading cutaneous induration¹⁵. These patients had more often ventilatory restriction and perimyositis. No significant relationship was detected between the eosinophil count and the extent of skin induration.

Thus we conclude that patients presenting with the skin thickening without Raynaud's phenomenon should be evaluated for EF. Presence of a groove sign suggests diagnosis of EF. Although skin biopsy is the gold standard for the diagnosis, newer imaging modalities like magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) clearly demonstrate the finding of fascial thickening in cases of EF and help in differentiating from other connective tissue disease. In addition, MRI also serves as a marker for disease activity, identifying disease relapse and appropriate response to therapy¹⁴. Though many agents have been used till date only corticosteroids have shown some benefit especially if used early in the course. Therefore there is a need for early diagnosis and treatment.

References

1. Shulman LE: Diffuse fasciitis with hypergammaglobulinemia and eosinophilia: a new syndrome? (Abstract). *J Rheumatol* 1974 1; suppl: 46.
2. Rizzo S. Eosinophilic pleuropericarditis and fasciitis: A new case. *Monaldi Arch Chest Dis* 2002; 57:311-3.
3. Killen JW, Swift GL, White RJ. Eosinophilic fasciitis and pleural involvement. *Postgrad Med J* 2000; 76: 37-7.
4. Michet CJ, Doyle JA, Ginsburg WW. Eosinophilic fasciitis. *Mayo Clin Proc* 1981; 56: 27-34.
5. Khanna D, Verity A, Grossman JM, et al. Eosinophilic fasciitis with multiple myeloma: a new hematological association. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2002; 61: 1111-2.
6. Hur JW, Lee HS, Uhm WS, Jun JB, Bae SC, Park Ck, Yoo DH. Eosinophilic fasciitis associated with autoimmune thyroiditis. *Korean J Intern Med* 2005; 20:180-2.
7. Di Gioacchino M, Masci S, Paolini F, Verna N, Angellucci D, Cavallucci E, Paganelli R. Common variable immunodeficiency and eosinophilic fasciitis. *Eur J Dermatol* 2002; 12: 73-4.
8. Choquet-Kastylevsky G, Kanitakis J, Dumas V, Faure M, Claudy A. Eosinophilic fasciitis and simvastatin. *Arch Intern Med* 2001; 161: 1456-7.
9. Cantini F, Salvarani C, Olivieri I, Padula A, Bellandi F, Palchetti R. Possible association between eosinophilic fasciitis and subcutaneous heparin use. *J Rheumatol* 1998; 25: 606-7.
10. Scleroderma and eosinophilic fasciitis in patients taking fosinopril. *J Rheumatol* 1997; 24:1242.
11. Kahari VM, Heino J, Niskanen L, Fraki J, Uitto J. Eosinophilic fasciitis. Increased collagen production and type I procollagen messenger RNA levels in fibroblasts cultured from involved skin. *Arch Dermatol* 1990; 126: 613- 7.
12. Peltonen J, Kahari L, Jakkola S, Kahari VM, Varga J, Uitto J, Jimenez SA. Evaluation of transforming growth factor beta and type I procollagen gene expression in fibrotic skin disease by in situ hybridization. *J Invest Dermatol* 1990; 94:365-71.
13. Jean-Francois V, Jean-Luc T, Valerie R, et al. Analysis of leukemia inhibitory factor, type I and type 2 cytokine production in patients with eosinophilic fasciitis. *J Rheumatol* 2001; 28:75-80.
14. Moulton SJ, Krandsdorf MJ, Ginsburg WW, Andy A, Persellin S. Eosinophilic fasciitis: Spectrum of MRI findings. *Am J Roentgenol* 2005; 184: 975-8.
15. Eosinophilic fasciitis: Analysis of a series of 10 patients. *Med Clin (Barc)* 2005; 125: 145-8.